

Project	GUTTA
Work Package number	WP2
Work Package title	Communication Activities
Deliverable number	2.1.3.
Deliverable title	Report with a strategy for communication activities
Deliverable Responsible Partner	AdSP-MAM
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Deliverable due date	2019-08-31
Deliverable latest review date	2020-03-12

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Scope of the GUTTA communication strategy is to facilitate the implementation of the project communication goals and make key stakeholders aware of the project's achievements.

To this end, the communication strategy designs and provide a guidance to both project internal and project external communication activities.

Scope of the internal communication is to facilitate an efficient and regular communication among GUTTA partners. Scope of the external communication is to create a network of project-external relationships and make key stakeholders aware of the project's outcomes.

The current report will therefore illustrate the main target groups, the communication channels to be used, and the communication activities planned in the framework of the project.

For the shortcuts employed in this report, we refer to the official GUTTA Glossary, which can be found at: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3667198

2. PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES OF THE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

2.1 Purposes and guiding principles

GUTTA's originality is to combine the strengths of Project Partners (PPs) from research organizations, industry, and the public sector in tackling key challenges for the territories and the environment. At the same time, this kind of partnership represents a challenge for the communication strategy. Its main purpose of the is to facilitate, with the contributions from all partners, the implementation of the project activities and make key stakeholders aware of the project's achievements.

The communication strategy is articulated in two parts:

- 1) the internal strategy, aiming to build bonding relationships as well as to ensure a smooth and efficient communication among the GUTTA partners;
- 2) the external strategy, with the purpose of bridging relationships externally to make key stakeholders aware of the project's results.

The guiding principles of these communication activities are openness, publicity, inclusiveness, and sustainability.

All PPs should participate in the Communication activities. The Interreg programme recommends “that **each project partner appoints one person responsible for communication.**” Internal **contact point** should be defined for IT and HR sides for multi-language activities and Deliverables. (e.g.: D2.2.1 Project Brochures; D2.2.2 Social platforms updates; D2.2.3 video/radio spots).

During the kick off meeting (KOM) of the project, on March 6-8, 2019, in Lecce, the communication contact points of the Partners and of the Advisory Board were assigned:

- **CMCC Foundation – Euro-Mediterranean Center of Climate Change**, Italy (Lead Partner): Mauro Buonocore, Laura Caciagli
- **Croatia Shipowners’ Association (CSA) Mare Nostrum**, Croatia: Maria Mihalić
- **University of Zadar (UniZd)**, Croatia: Martin Zrilić
- **Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure (MMPI, also termed MSTI in the AF) – Maritime Safety Directorate**, Croatia: Davor Dezeljin, Mladena Maracic
- **Southern Adriatic Sea Port Authority (AdSP-MAM, Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare Adriatico Meridionale)**, Italy: Lia Piteni
- **European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)**: Ann MacPherson

2.2 Objectives of internal communication

The internal communication strategy outlines GUTTA’s overall approach for communicating with PPs and specifies the communication tools we will use in order to achieve our goals.

The main objectives of the internal communication strategy are in particular:

- a) To guarantee that the GUTTA partners are updated on all ongoing activities;
- b) To ensure good relationships and fruitful exchanges among the partners;
- c) To develop a sense of common purpose between the partners, and encourage all partners to commit to the realization of the common goals.
- d) To set up the communication guidelines/channels to be used among the GUTTA partners.

The Lead Partner (LP) will coordinate the activities together with Work Package (WP) and activities leaders, allowing a continuous stream of internal communication. Close cooperation will be allowed by direct participation and communication (emails, webexes and tools such as Slack, Dropbox, and Google Drive). The status of the art will be discussed with the help of web-meetings, using e.g. the CISCO platform of the LP. Every deliverable is under the responsibility of one Project Partner (PP), acting under the control of the WP leader.

In view of the specific contribution of GUTTA to environmental sustainability, PPs will commit themselves to report to the LP their estimated CO2 emissions due to travels for internal project meetings and project related events. This will raise the partnership’s awareness of the environmental impact and the high ethical meaning of their project activities for the Programme area and beyond.

2.3 Objectives of external communication

External communication and dissemination are critical aspects of GUTTA project overall.

General objectives of the communication strategy are:

- To inform media and general public about the results of the project;
- To spread information on the Project in the areas interested by the Programme;
- To increase the circulation of the information about the innovative contribution of the project;
- To promote specific events or activities.

The specific external communication objectives are in particular:

- To increase an effective involvement of ship-owners, shipping company and different private and public stakeholders of the maritime sector in the implementation of the EU regulation on MRV of CO2 emissions;
- To improve the general awareness on the sustainable use of eco-routes and new link in the Adriatic Region;
- To disseminate technical knowledge on the potential of saving fuel and emission in the maritime transport.

GUTTA is aware of the potential and responsibility of CB cooperation projects with respect to the European Cohesion Policy, as recently stressed also by a communication of the EU Council (7896/17).

The actual communication contents will be based on bottom-up contributions by the individual partners. A selection of project internal communication outputs will be integrated to Programme and eventually external communication outputs.

The interaction with the stakeholders and the public will always strive to be bi-directional, in order to maximize involvement and feedback collection. In particular, the target group of maritime professionals/institutions and under- 40 citizens will be part of the consultation process for the assessment of what new routes are more advantageous for the territory, with a holistic evaluation of both economic, social, infrastructural, and development criteria and needs. Dedicated dissemination events will complement the communication strategy.

All GUTTA partners will actively contribute to the communication activities, led by AdSP-MAM in its function of WP2 leader.

Some specific activities of partners will include:

- Creation of a stakeholders' database, communication strategy, posts on social platforms, and report of public events by AdSP-MAM;
- Preparation of press releases and production of video or radio spots (2 in IT, 2 in HR); submission of scientific journal papers by CMCC and UniZd.

3. TARGET GROUPS

3.1 Internal target groups

The target group for the internal communication is the set of GUTTA's partners, i.e.:

- CMCC Foundation – Euro-Mediterranean Center of Climate Change, Italy (Lead Partner)
- Croatia Shipowners' Association (CSA) Mare Nostrum, Croatia
- University of Zadar (UniZd), Croatia
- Ministry of the Sea, Transport and Infrastructure (MSTI) – Maritime Safety Directorate, Croatia
- Southern Adriatic Sea Port Authority (AdSP-MAM Autorità di Sistema Portuale del Mare Adriatico Meridionale), Italy

Eventually, EMSA in its function of member of the Advisory Board, will be included to this group.

3.2 External target groups

The external communication strategy targets the stakeholders interested, such as the citizens of Italy and Croatia, the passengers of Adriatic routes, the operators of the maritime sector and the technical communities related to maritime transport, control engineering, and environmental forecasting and assessment, that is all the communities interested in improving quality, safety and environmental sustainability of marine and coastal transport services.

More in detail, they can be classified as follows:

- a) **Professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector;**
- b) **General public** (i.e. passengers, consumers), with a **special focus on Under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia;**
- c) **Research community and academia.**

a) Stakeholders of the maritime sector

Here is a tentative list, including some stakeholders that have been already informed about GUTTA and will be prone to collaborate:

- EC Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE)
- IT Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport
- Croatian Register of Shipping
- Port of Zadar Authority
- County Port Authority of Zadar

- City of Zadar
- Regione Puglia, Settore Trasporti
- Italian Coast Guard, Direzione Marittima di Bari
- International Maritime Organization (IMO)
- SNAV s.p.a.
- Jadrolinija
- European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)
- HR Ministry of the Environment and Energy
- European Community Shipowners Association (ECSA)
- DNV-GL
- Comune di Bari
- Comune di Manfredonia
- Comune di Monopoli
- Interferry
- Escola Europea de Short Sea Shipping (2E3S.eu)

Other possible stakeholders may be found at <https://twitter.com/VISIRnavi/following>

The communication strategy of the project will aim at:

- a) showing the strength of meteo-marine forecasts for a tailor-made decision support system that optimizes vessel emissions;
- b) showing the potential benefits from sharing onboard vessel performance data;
- c) showing evidence of key traffic and logistic data useful for assessing the feasibility of new links and eco-routes in the Adriatic Region.

Tactics / Approach:

- Dissemination of project's aims and results via public events and press-releases (KOM, EC-day, final events in IT and HR);
- Increasing the opportunity of networking and exchange of good practices;
- Direct communication with specific media relations will improve the message from technical events and reports in order to widen the coverage;
- Display of video, posters, and other visual dissemination publicity material on board ferries as well as on land at the terminals (i.e. touristic and cargo terminals).

b) General public and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia

Here a preliminary list:

- Under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia;
- General public (i.e. passengers, consumers);

During the IT-HR Programme kick-off meeting (Nov. 2016) Agnes Monfret of DG REGIO (Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy) discussed statistical data indicating that this social group has a scarce awareness of EU-funded CB programmes. GUTTA will target also this group, aiming at raising the awareness of the beneficial effect of the EU cohesion policy.

Multimedia messages, social media campaign and publicity will be crucial to reach general public.

Tactics / Approach:

- Social/radio/video marketing for raising visibility and publicity. A broader audience will be engaged through social media and local press in different languages (IT-HR-EN), with clear and easy messages. Specific display will be performed on board on passengers' ships, as well as at the touristic terminals.
- Participation to the EC Day - European cooperation day (www.ecday.eu) in 2019.

c) Research community and academia

A smart and inclusive blue growth in the Adriatic region cannot be accomplished in the long term without securing the availability and circulation of high- skilled human resources and without facilitating the industry-research cooperation.

The technical and scientific advancements will be focused on the evidence of saving fuel and emission in the transport.

The Decision Support System (DSS) for planning of eco-routes will be distributed to experts (i.e. engineering and maritime transport related universities and research centers) to be validated, assessed and to receive feedbacks.

Tactics / Approach:

- Maintaining community relations via participation to conferences and workshops; invitation of experts to GUTTA project events, facilitating networking and long-lasting relationships.
- Dissemination via publication of technical reports and journal articles

4. KEY MESSAGES

GUTTA external communication strategy will tailor four key messages to specific groups of stakeholders. A driving concept is that the maritime transport is crucial for climate and quality of life addressing decarbonisation and energy efficiency. The GUTTA project will design, implement, and make available an eco-route Decision Support System. Therefore, the project outputs can have a positive environmental impact.

4.1 First message

First and foremost, it is important to highlight to all target groups that the GUTTA project will address the disparities in accessibility between the shores of the Adriatic Region (Cooperation Programme (CP), pag.10-17; Factsheet 5, Annex IV). As long as Italy-Croatia are concerned, just the Bari-Dubrovnik route exists in the southern part of the basin, while Pescara, Ancona, Pesaro, Ravenna, and Venice are all directly connected, at least seasonally, to Croatian ports such as Umag, Rovinj, Zadar, Stari Grad.

GUTTA will tackle the challenge of re-balancing these disparities by a cross-border institutional coordination that shall improve the framework for encouraging the ship operators to fill this gap.

The project should contribute to raise the public attention on this topic. The message to the general public should be concise and simple, showing the importance of maritime transport and the potential work to be done in this field.

4.2 Second message

The second key message is that maritime transport decarbonisation and energy efficiency are essential for global growth and sustainability and can have a great environmental positive impact.

The EU requires the vessels above 5000 GT (e.g. ferries) to monitor, report, and verify their CO₂ emissions (Regulation 757/2015), setting a temporal road-map and the framework conditions for these activities. The same regulation entrusts EMSA with the task to collect and publish the data provided by the shipowners with collaboration of the verification authorities. This is done through the thetis MRV portal, <https://mrv.emsa.europa.eu/#public/eumrv>

For the first time, on June 30, 2019, EMSA published these CO₂ emission data from ships calling at and from European ports. It is now necessary to fully understand such a new information, and to value and disseminate it also to the broader public.

Also, in agreement with what discussed during the GUTTA KOM, EMSA will appreciate a feedback on the thetis-MRV system provided by the shipowners and other stakeholders, and collected through the GUTTA project.

4.3 Third message

The project will foster innovation realizing a pilot-action for planning of eco-routes: GUTTA will directly contribute to the reduction of the CO₂ emissions from ferry boats through the development of a new DSS. It will make use of the knowledge of the forecast meteo-marine conditions for computing routes that minimize CO₂ emissions. This project output will address both the goals of energy efficiency and decarbonisation (CP, pagg. 14, 16, 17; Factsheet 5, Annex V) and the cross-cutting issue of ICT development in the Programme Area (CP, pag. 17; Factsheet 5, Annex V). In particular, the operational tool for the optimization of maritime routes represents an eco-innovation, which is not yet available neither in the academia nor in the industry. Furthermore, the existing knowledge basis of the maritime traffic from the public sector's representatives of Italy and Croatia will be merged and analyzed, providing an objective assessment for decision-making and interaction with the private sector (ship operators). Publicity and openness of the source code of the tool for eco-routes should contribute to scale up the project results and their impact on society, contributing to decarbonization targets for ferryboats in other European regions too.

4.4 Fourth message

GUTTA may include a potential for job creation related to the establishment of a new maritime link between Italy and Croatia. While its operation is not planned during the project lifetime, GUTTA will favor it by analysis of traffic and by coordination of private and Institutional stakeholders. In the long run, this may result in job creation in the field of vessel piloting, harbor services, local public transport and tourism. Thus, a successful implementation of this specific objective of GUTTA project would also represent a social innovation for the involved territories of Italy and Croatia.

5. MEANS AND ACTIVITIES FOR EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

5.1 Activity details 2.1 “Start-up activities”

The communication start-up activities will comprise:

- identification of the thematic contents that will be object of the communication efforts;
- preparation of a list of stakeholders;
- definition of the periodicity of public updates;
- the press release of the kick off meeting.

Deliverables

2.1.1 Press release of the project kick-off meeting [PP in charge: CMCC, delivery: M03]

2.1.2 Stakeholders database [AdSP-MAM, M08]

2.1.3 Report with a strategy for communication activities **[AdSP-MAM, M08]**

5.2 Activity details 2.2 “External communication”

GUTTA aims and results will be externally disseminated via:

- printed and electronic format brochures (IT-HR-ENG);
- online publications on national magazines;
- press-releases and production of video or radio-spots;
- documentation of the model advancements in peer-reviewed scientific journals.
- the GUTTA project section on Interreg Italy Croatia programme website will be regularly updated.

Deliverables

2.2.1 Project brochures (EN-IT-HR) **[UniZd + all partners (content), M10]**

2.2.2 Social media (IT-HR programme website, Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn etc.), in EN, IT, and HR language **[AdSP-MAM + all partners (content), M15]**

2.2.3 Video or radio spots for either local, national, web broadcasters, at least 2 in IT and 2 in HR **[CMCC + all partners (contents), M24]**

2.2.4 Press release of IT final event **[AdSP-MAM, M29]**

2.2.5 Press release of HR final event **[MSTI, M30]**

2.2.6 Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper **[CMCC, M30]**

2.2.7 Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper **[UniZd, M30]**

5.3 Activity details 2.3 “Direct engagement of stakeholders”

GUTTA will engage with its stakeholders from both the industry and the institutions through three large-scale events:

- participation to the EC-Day of year 2019 **[M10]**;
- organization of the two final public events **[M29, M30]**, one of them being at the premises of the Ministry of Sea, Transport and Infrastructure in Zagreb.

These events will not just disseminate GUTTA results but will also actively engage with the stakeholders, listening to them with questionnaires, structured interviews, and on-stage invitation. Representatives from all three GUTTA’s target groups, including citizens, maritime professionals and institutions, and scientists will also be invited at these events. The inputs from the final events will be considered in view of making the legacy of GUTTA even more enduring.

Deliverables

2.3.1 Final report on the outcome of all GUTTA public events [AdSP-MAM, M30]

D2.2.1 Brochure

D2.2.2 Social Media

D2.2.3 video/radio spots

See the chapter “Purposes and objectives of the communication” to see the communication contact points that have been assigned for each project partner.

5.4 Communication channels

1) Mailing list

Responsible partner: CMCC

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, research community and academia, and the media.

Address: gutta-ext@cmcc.it

Description: This mailing list serves the purpose of ensuring a regular and smooth external dissemination (the version released for D.2.1.2 “Stakeholders database” includes about 100 members, and will be further populated by AdSP-MAM during the project implementation).

2) Project website

Related deliverables: D. 2.2.2 Social media (IT-HR programme website, Twitter, Facebook, etc.), in EN, IT, and HR language [AdSP-MAM, M15]

Responsible partner: CMCC + all the project communication contact points (content)

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, research community and academia, and the media.

Address: <https://www.cmcc.it/projects/gutta-saving-fuel-and-emissions-from-maritime-transport-in-the-adriatic-region> and <https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta>

Description: The Interreg Italy Croatia Programme provides a project website (<https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/gutta>) integrated and hosted on the Programme website, a platform on which the project will be able to publish information about project management, deliverables, outputs, results, events, news and databases, capacity building information. The platform will be one of the external means of communication: it will be the main channel for the dissemination of the scientific outcomes of the project, hosting all the contents produced: news, events, video and radio spots, etc.

CMCC will be the main responsible for its management/update (on a regular basis); however, all partners are responsible for providing the contents (deliverables, tools and other materials) to be shared on website (in English).

All the projects of the Interreg Italy Croatia Programme are [available here](#).

All the projects of the Priority Axis Maritime Transport / SO 4.1. are [available here](#).

3) Social media

Related deliverables: D. 2.2.2 Social media (IT-HR programme website, Twitter, Facebook, etc.), in EN, IT, and HR language [AdSP-MAM, M15]

Responsible partner: all partners

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular the general public (and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia) and professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, and the media.

Addresses:

- Twitter handles: [@CmccClimate](#), [@AdSPMAM](#), [@VISIRnavi](#)
- Other: <https://www.facebook.com/CmccClimate/>, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12226084/>, <https://www.researchgate.net/project/GUTTA-savinG-fUel-and-emissions-from-mariTime-Transport-in-the-Adriatic-region>

Description: The project partners will use, develop and animate the LinkedIn page “[Interreg Italy-Croatia GUTTA project](#)” and the Research Gate page “[GUTTA-savinG fUel and emissions from mariTime Transport in the Adriatic region](#)” accounts. Given the large number of followers on existing Facebook and Twitter accounts of the projects partners, this web presence will also be exploited to spread updates from the project. The aim is to inform and engage with stakeholders and the media. The networking activity on social media will target specific categories of stakeholders in order to collect information useful for the project database and enlarge the network by involving new interested parties.

Twitter activities will be fast and interactive, thanks to the incorporation of hashtags and they will target all stakeholders with all key messages. LinkedIn will be more corporate-oriented, with a slower pace in the publication and targeting professionals and other organisations involved in the maritime sector. Facebook will be suitable for visual storytelling (videos, photos and infographics) and they should target in particular the general public and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia. Some hashtags to be used will be for example #maritime #transport #ferries #minimizeCO2 #GUTTA #Interreg #forecasts #ItalyCroatia.

Social platform updates will be in English, Italian and Croatian.

4) Press office and media relation

Related Deliverables:

D. 2.1.1 Press release of kick-off meeting [PP in charge: CMCC, delivery: M03]

D. 2.2.4 Press release of IT final event [AdSP-MAM, M29]

D. 2.2.5 Press release of HR final event [MSTI, M30]

Responsible partner: CMCC, AdSP-MAM, MSTI + all partners (providing contents)

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, the general public (and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia) and the media.

Description: A press release will be developed for each event planned by the project (e.g. the kick-off meeting and the two final events in Italy and Croatia) and for the events organized by the Interreg Italy Croatia Programme in order to reach out to local/national/EU media and get appropriate coverage, thus

contributing to raising awareness within the general public. The press kit should be differentiated according to events' targeted stakeholders. Press releases will be in English, Italian and Croatian.

5) Printed and electronic materials (brochures, posters, peer-reviewed articles etc)

Related deliverables:

D. 2.2.1 Project brochures (EN-IT-HR) [UniZd, M10]

D. 2.2.6 Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper [CMCC, M30]

D. 2.2.7 Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper [UniZd, M30]

Responsible partner: UniZd, CMCC + all partners (providing contents)

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, the general public (and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia) and the media.

Description:

A project brochure (in printed and electronic format) will be realized in English. More in detail, the project brochure will be at least bilingual, EN-IT and EN-HR.

Scientific advancements will be highlighted in peer-reviewed scientific journals.

In addition to the press kit, a poster will be created to present the project and its main objectives. The design will be based on Interreg Italy Croatia Programme template. The Programme will provide the project with:

a) Logo and design templates for publications (event invitations, posters, etc.) and promotional materials, which can be easily adapted and implemented;

b) Project Communication kit includes:

Project Brand Manual, defining all the branding requirements and brand elements and setting out the rules for correct use and application of the logo;

Logos (in different versions: CMYK, Greyscale, Negative, Black and white);

Fund label (in different versions: CMYK, Greyscale, Negative, Black and white);

Office pack (word, excel, ppt), adaptable to partnerships' needs;

Poster (the design template provided in InDesign and pdf formats, modifiable with simple graphic design programs);

Invitation (InDesign and pdf formats, modifiable with simple graphic design programs);

Cover;

Key Visual;

Programme Area Map;

Thematic Priority Icons.

6) Multimedia materials

Related deliverables: D. 2.2.3 Video or radio spots for either local, national, web broadcasters, at least 2 in IT and 2 in HR [CMCC, M24]

Responsible partner: CMCC + all partners (content)

Target groups: stakeholders, in particular professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector, the general public (and especially under-40-years-old EU citizens of Italy and Croatia) and the media.

Description:

Two videos or radio spots should be produced during the project:

1. Containing aims of GUTTA and an invitation to join it as a stakeholder;
2. Disseminating GUTTA results, including interviews taken during SC and final events.

Therefore, the video could be a short promotional audio-visual presentation of the project, or a video realized during an event (e.g. video streaming of the events, partners and stakeholder's interviews at key events). The promotional video could be realized in a middle stage, in order to have enough information and results achieved so far and, at the same time, to be used as a promotional tool for the continuation of the project.

Radio spots could be broadcast through Internet as podcasts (e.g. using the portal "[Shipping podcast – voices from the maritime industry](#)"), enormously broadening their reach.

7) Project database

Related deliverables: D. 2.1.2 Stakeholders database [AdSP-MAM, M08]

Responsible partner: AdSP-MAM

Target groups: professionals and institutional actors of the maritime sector

Description: The project database will contain all the relevant information about maritime stakeholders. Moreover, the database can be populated during the organization and the participation to events, but also by means of web search and identification of potential stakeholders. The database should be as rich as possible as it should serve as the base on which all the other activities will be built upon. AdSP-MAM will be responsible for the project database. The collection of this information will take into account privacy protection issues and will be carried out in compliance with the related EU and national regulations.

8) Events

The main objective of this activity is to facilitate the exchange of information among stakeholders and the dissemination of their activity into a wide public-private sphere.

More in detail, GUTTA will engage with its stakeholders from both the industry and the institutions through three large-scale events:

- the [EC-Day 2019 \(M09\) or 2020](#) (M10);
- the organization of the two closure events (M29, M30), one of them being at the premises of the Ministry of Sea, Transport and Infrastructure in Zagreb;
- The organization of webinars to disseminate the main outcomes of the project.

These events will not just disseminate GUTTA results but will also actively engage with the stakeholders, listening to them with questionnaires, structured interviews, and on-stage invitation. Representatives from all three GUTTA's target groups, including citizens, maritime professionals and institutions, and scientists will also be invited at these events. The inputs from the final events will be considered in view of making the legacy of GUTTA even more enduring.

Beside the closure events, GUTTA could participate to other events such as other Interreg Italy Croatia programme events, and other important initiatives and events such as EC-Day , ESO2020, EU Maritime Days, etc. Participation should be coordinated among PP, in order to avoid overlapping, rationalize expenses and optimizing results.

6. MEANS AND ACTIVITIES FOR INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

1) Mailing lists

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: The mailing lists:

- gutta@cmcc.it, including all PP members (about 30 members)
- gutta-sc@cmcc.it: Including SC members and Advisory Board (about 10 members)
- gutta-comm@cmcc.it, including PP communication contact points (about 10 members)

serve the purpose of ensuring regular and smooth internal communication between the partners, as well as to keep track on the project progresses, and create greater synergies between the partners. These email lists should be used at least once per month, in order to exchange necessary information and coordinate on the ongoing and upcoming activities of the project. Note that as soon as the Web Platform will be available, we will use also the sharing tools provided in it.

2) Web-based videoconferencing tools

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: In order to secure smooth and frequent communications between the project partners and Lead partner, web-based conferencing tools such as WebEx[®] or GotoMeeting[®] or CISCO should be used in order to hold regular conference calls. The conference calls should be organized at least once per month; the date of next conference call is decided either during the conference call itself or through Doodle tool. Agenda is usually set and sent to partners by the coordinator at least one day prior to the call. The partner calling the conference (usually but not exclusively, the coordinator) should take minutes of the conference call and send it to all the GUTTA partners as soon as possible.

3) Dropbox

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: Each partner wishing to regularly update certain strategy documents and easily share them with project partners.

Description: During the project's lifecycle, some documents will need regular updates as some time frames might change, roles might shift etc. This is why these documents should be uploaded online via Dropbox and shared with all the parties in charge of documenting the changes/updates.

The following is a non-exhaustive list of documents suitable for sharing via Dropbox:

- a) External communication strategy (shared between partners; partner in charge of updating: AdSP-MAM).
- b) Internal Gantt chart (shared first between partners; partner in charge of updating: all the partners. Changes to the chart need to be approved by the coordinator).

4) Google Docs

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: Google Docs should be used to store important large files and documents on project management, deliverables, outputs, results, events, news and databases. The GUTTA Google Docs folder should be used as internal means of communication; the documents shared through Dropbox should not be uploaded on the Google Docs folder until they reach their final and consolidated version. CMCC will be the sole responsible for its management/update (on a regular basis); however, the other partners are responsible to provide the files and documents (deliverables, tools and other materials).

5) Internal Gantt Chart

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: A Gantt chart has been prepared (see Table 1). The Internal Gantt Chart is consistent with the application form, and documents all the activities and deliverables in due timeframe. In this manner, the partners can have the overview of when the tasks/deliverables are due and if they have started when planned. In addition, the internal Gantt Chart provides a clear view of the distribution of work between the project partners.

The 'final' product should later on be uploaded as Google Sheets and given access to all the partners in order for them to be able to update it regularly. In this way, they would always have an instant access to the latest version of the document, in case some timeframes or data would change.

6) Internal formatting rules and templates

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: In order to create a unified look of all the documents created under the GUTTA project, unified formatting rules and templates should be created to be used by all the partners. By this, we will ensure that all the tasks and deliverables are formatted in the same manner, which makes them easier to be evaluated and compared. These formatting rules and templates will be consistent with the Interrg Italy Croatia Programme formatting rules. A deliverable template has already been implemented.

7) Slack

Responsible partners: CMCC

Target groups: GUTTA project partners

Description: Moreover, GUTTA partners will use Slack for the internal organization of work (gutta-project.slack.com). Slack will be a useful channel for organized conversations; partners will be able to drag-and-drop PDFs, images, videos and other files directly into Slack, or get feedback on their work and create an archive of project progress.

Activities and deliverables		PP in charge	Target value	Due date
2.1	Start-up activities			
2.1.1	Press release of the kick off meeting	CMCC	1	03-2019
2.1.2	Stakeholders database	AdSP-MAM	1	08-2019
2.1.3	Report with a strategy for communication activities	AdSP-MAM	1	08-2019
2.2	External communication			
2.2.1	Project brochures (EN-IT-HR)	UniZd	2 EN-IT; EN-HR	10-2019
2.2.2	Online updates (website + social platforms)	AdSP-MAM		project lifelong
2.2.3	video or radio spots, 2 in IT and 2 in HR	CMCC	4	12-2020
2.2.4	Press release of the IT final event	AdSP-MAM	1	05-2021
2.2.5	Press release of the HR final event	MSTI	1	06-2021
2.2.6	Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper	CMCC	1	06-2021
2.2.7	Submission of 1 open-access peer-reviewed and/or conference paper	UniZd	1	06-2021
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders			
2.3.1	Final report on the outcome of all GUTTA public events	AdSP-MAM	1	06-2021

Tables 4-8: Budget for WP2

STAFF COSTS			M01-06	M07-12	M13-18	M19-24	M25-30	TOTAL
CMCC		Timeframe	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 15.000,00	€ 21.000,00	€ 54.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 6.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 6.000,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 6.000,00	€ 24.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 9.000,00	€ 15.000,00	€ 24.000,00
CSA		Timeframe	€ 6.000,00	€ 5.000,00	€ 2.500,00	€ 5.000,00	€ 4.500,00	€ 23.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 6.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 8.000,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 2.500,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 2.500,00	€ 11.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 4.000,00
UNI ZADAR		Timeframe	€ 3.000,00	€ 4.500,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 7.500,00	€ 8.500,00	€ 27.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 3.000,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 4.000,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 14.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 4.000,00	€ 5.000,00	€ 9.000,00
MINISTRY SEA		Timeframe	€ 900,00	€ 1.900,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 7.800,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 900,00	€ 900,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.800,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 4.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 2.000,00
AdSP		Timeframe	€ 5.000,00	€ 5.500,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 4.000,00	€ 4.000,00	€ 20.500,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 5.000,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 8.500,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 8.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 4.000,00

TRAVEL COSTS			M01-06	M07-12	M13-18	M19-24	M25-30	TOTAL
CMCC		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 5.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 5.000,00
CSA		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 2.100,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 2.100,00
UNI ZADAR		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.900,00	€ 3.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.900,00	€ 3.000,00
MINISTRY SEA		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 3.100,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.000,00	€ 3.100,00
AdSP		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.700,00	€ 3.800,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.100,00	€ 0,00	€ 2.700,00	€ 3.800,00

EXTERNAL EXPERTISE and SERVICE COSTS			M01-06	M07-12	M13-18	M19-24	M25-30	TOTAL
CMCC		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 2.200,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 30.000,00	€ 33.700,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 2.200,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 500,00	€ 4.200,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 29.500,00	€ 29.500,00
CSA		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 1.700,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.800,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.500,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 1.700,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.800,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.500,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
UNI ZADAR		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 2.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 4.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 2.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.500,00	€ 0,00	€ 4.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
MINISTRY SEA		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 1.600,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.650,00	€ 25.000,00	€ 28.250,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 1.600,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.650,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.250,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 25.000,00	€ 25.000,00
AdSP		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 1.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00

EQUIPMENT EXPENDITURE			M01-06	M07-12	M13-18	M19-24	M25-30	TOTAL
CSA		Timeframe	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00
2.1	Start-up activities	M1-M8	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00
2.2	External communication	M9-M30	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00
2.3	Direct engagement of stakeholders	M15-M30	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00

BL /partner	CMCC	CSA	UNI ZADAR	MINISTRY SEA	AdSP	TOTAL
Staff costs	€ 54.000,00	€ 23.000,00	€ 27.000,00	€ 7.800,00	€ 20.500,00	€ 132.300,00
Office and administrative expenditure	€ 8.100,00	€ 3.450,00	€ 4.050,00	€ 1.170,00	€ 3.075,00	€ 19.845,00
Travel and accommodation costs	€ 5.000,00	€ 2.100,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 3.100,00	€ 3.800,00	€ 17.000,00
External expertise and services costs	€ 33.700,00	€ 3.500,00	€ 4.000,00	€ 28.250,00	€ 1.000,00	€ 70.450,00
Equipment expenditure	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 0,00	€ 3.000,00
	€ 100.800,00	€ 35.050,00	€ 38.050,00	€ 40.320,00	€ 28.375,00	€ 242.595,00

8. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

All the activities related to each means of communication should be monitored in order to evaluate their effectiveness. The following sets of indicators will keep track of the evolution of the project, comparing it with reference targets.

Table 9: List of output indicators

Activities	Indicator	Target values
Web platform	N. of (fully) activated platform	1
Project Database	N. stakeholders listed in the DB	300
Press Kit and Poster	N. of project posters developed	3
	N. of project press kits developed	3
Videos	N. of video / radio spots commissioned	2 + 2
Social Networks	N. of monthly posts on Facebook	2
	N. of monthly tweet on Twitter	2
	N. of monthly posts on LinkedIn	1
Webinars	N. of organized webinars	1
Public events	N. of public events	3
Peer-reviewed papers for project results documentation	N. journal papers submitted	2

Internal Mailing list	Consistency of usage	2/month
Web-based videoconferencing tools	Consistency of conference calls	1/month
	N. of partners present at each conference call	2-3

Besides the monitoring indicators, different reports should be produced in order to adequately evaluate the communication activities (e.g.: progress reports, SC meeting reports etc).